

Varietal response to different nitrogen management methods in an irrigated transplanted rice ecosystem in a Vertisol, Andhra Pradesh, India

R.M. Kumar, K. Padmaja, S.V. Subbaiah, Directorate of Rice Research (DRR), Hyderabad 500030, Andhra Pradesh, India; and V. Balasubramanian, IRR

Nitrogen (N) fertilizer is a major input for rice. Only 30–40% of applied N is used by the crop, however, due to losses through volatilization, denitrification, leaching, and runoff (De Datta and Buresh 1989). Deep placement of urea, split N application, preplanting incorporation of coated and controlled-release urea (CRU), and the chlorophyll meter and leaf color chart techniques are some N management strategies that could reduce N losses and improve fertilizer use efficiency in rice (Katyal et al 1985, Kumar et al 1989, Peng et al 1996, Balasubramanian et al 1999). Since rice varieties differ in N use efficiency (NUE), this study was conducted to determine their response to selected N management techniques.

Field trials were conducted at the DRR farm, Andhra Pradesh, India, during the 1997 monsoon (kharif, July to October) and 1997-98 winter (rabi, November to February/March) seasons. The soil at the experimental site is a typical Vertisol, with a pH of 8.3, cation exchange capacity (CEC) 45 cmol P⁺ kg⁻¹, organic carbon 5.5 g kg⁻¹, available (KMnO₄-extractable) N 150 kg ha⁻¹, Olsen P 30.4 kg ha⁻¹, and NH₄Ac-extractable K 244.5 kg ha⁻¹.

Five N treatments were evaluated: zero-N control, controlled-release urea with 4.5% and 6% coating, chlorophyll meter-guided N, and prilled urea (PU) applied in two equal splits. The CRU fertilizers had 43% N, 1.3% biuret, 120 ppm free ammonia, 0.08% moisture, and 1.8% conditioner. The two CRUs were broadcast at the rate of 86 kg N ha⁻¹ and incorporated into the soil just before planting. PU (100 kg N ha⁻¹) was applied in two equal splits: 50% basal and 50% topdressing at the maximum tillering stage.

Three rice varieties were used: Rasi (short duration, 105 d, and yield potential of 6.5 t ha⁻¹), Ajaya (medium duration, 135 d, and yield potential of 7.5 t ha⁻¹), and Pusa Basmati (improved aromatic variety, 145 d, and yield potential of 4.5 t ha⁻¹). All varieties were transplanted at 20 × 10-cm spacing. The two-factor factorial was organized in a randomized block design with three replications.

In all treatments, chlorophyll meter readings were taken weekly starting from 14 d after transplanting (DAT) until first flowering using the youngest fully expanded leaf of 10 randomly selected plants in each plot. For the SPAD method, N was applied when measured mean SPAD values fell below the threshold of 35 for each of the three varieties. The amount of N applied in the SPAD treatment varied with season and crop growth stages. The rate per application was 20, 30, and 20 kg N ha⁻¹ in the monsoon season and 30, 35, and 20 kg N ha⁻¹ in the winter season at the early (14–28 DAT), rapid (29–48 DAT), and late growth stages (49 DAT-first flowering), respectively. Phosphorus (P) and potassium (K) were applied in all plots at locally recommended rates of 27 kg P and 32 kg K ha⁻¹. Locally recommended practices were used for all other field operations and crop care.

In the SPAD treatments, the total amount of N applied to varieties Ajaya and Rasi was 70 kg ha⁻¹ in the monsoon and 75 kg ha⁻¹ in winter. A lower amount was applied to Pusa Basmati—50 kg ha⁻¹ in the monsoon and 65 kg ha⁻¹ in winter. For short-duration Rasi, CRU 6% and SPAD-35 N gave higher grain yields than other treatments in both seasons (Table 1). Yield performances of CRU 4.5% and CRU 6%

were comparable in the winter season. The mean increase in grain yield over PU-2 splits was 26% for SPAD-35 N, 24% for CRU 6%, and 7% for CRU 4.5%. The mean agronomic efficiency of applied N (AEN) and partial factor productivity for N (PFP-N) were highest in the SPAD-35 N treatment, followed closely by CRU 6% (Table 1). Plant N uptake was highest (111.8 kg N ha⁻¹) in Rasi fertilized with CRU 6%; it had an N recovery of 87.4%.

The response of medium-duration Ajaya to N application was better than that of the other two varieties in both seasons (Table 1). Application of CRU 6% produced a mean grain yield over two seasons of 6.3 t ha⁻¹, compared with 5.9 t ha⁻¹ for SPAD-35 N, 5.7 t ha⁻¹ for CRU 4.5%, and 5.6 t ha⁻¹ for PU-2 splits. In the monsoon season, CRU 6% gave the highest grain yield, which was on a par with CRU 4.5% but significantly superior to the other treatments. In the winter season, grain yields of CRU 6% and SPAD-35 N (6.8 t ha⁻¹ each) were significantly higher than those of PU-2 splits and CRU 4.5% (5.9 t ha⁻¹ each). The AEN and PFP-N values of these treatments showed a similar trend (Table 1). Mean AEN and PFP-N values over two seasons were highest in the SPAD-35 N treatment, followed closely by CRU 6%. Plant N uptake, however, was highest in CRU 6% (110.0 kg N ha⁻¹), followed by the SPAD-35 N treatment (93.5 kg N ha⁻¹).

The aromatic rice variety Pusa Basmati was the least responsive to various N treatments. The CRU 6% and SPAD-35 N treatments produced the highest grain yield in the monsoon and winter, respectively, followed by PU-2 splits. The single application of CRU 4.5% was less efficient than the other methods.

Table 1. Response of three rice varieties to different N management methods in irrigated transplanted rice at the DRR farm, Andhra Pradesh, India, 1997-98.^a

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)			Total N uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)			Recovery (%) ^b			AEN ^c			PFP-N ^d		
	1997 kharif	1997-98 rabi	Mean	1997 kharif	1997-98 rabi	Mean	1997 kharif	1997-98 rabi	Mean	1997 kharif	1997-98 rabi	Mean	1997 kharif	1997-98 rabi	Mean
Rasi															
Control	1.9 c	2.0 c	2.0	37.1 e	36.2e	36.6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CRU 4.5%	3.5 b	5.5 ab	4.5	79.3 c	97.8 d	88.6	49.1	71.6	60.3	18.3	40.5	29.4	40.8	64.2	52.5
CRU 6%	4.3 a	5.9 a	5.1	91.4 a	132.3 a	111.8	63.1	111.7	87.4	27.4	44.7	36.1	50.0	68.4	59.2
SPAD-35 N	4.8 a	5.8 a	5.3	83.7 b	125.5 b	104.6	66.5	119.0	92.8	40.4	50.3	45.3	68.1	77.5	72.8
PU-2 splits	3.3 b	5.1 b	4.2	61.6 d	114.3 c	87.9	24.5	78.1	51.3	13.5	30.5	22.0	32.8	50.9	41.8
Mean	3.6	4.9	4.2	70.6	101.2	85.9	50.8	95.1	73.0	24.9	41.5	33.2	47.9	65.2	56.6
Ajaya															
Control	2.4 c	2.2 c	2.3	37.6 d	28.2 d	32.9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CRU 4.5%	5.5 ab	5.9 b	5.7	93.5 b	80.1 c	86.8	65.0	60.3	62.7	36.3	43.0	39.7	63.7	68.4	66.1
CRU 6%	5.7 a	6.8 a	6.3	103.5 a	116.5 a	110.0	76.6	102.7	89.6	39.3	53.3	46.3	66.7	78.6	72.7
SPAD-35 N	5.0 b	6.8 a	5.9	87.0 c	100.0 b	93.5	70.6	95.7	83.2	37.7	60.9	49.3	71.4	90.0	80.7
PU-2 splits	5.4 ab	5.9 b	5.6	88.1 c	79.9 c	84.0	50.5	51.7	51.1	29.0	37.5	33.3	53.5	59.3	56.4
Mean	4.8	5.5	5.1	81.9	80.9	81.4	65.7	77.6	71.6	35.6	48.7	42.1	63.8	74.1	69.0
Pusa Basmati															
Control	1.4 c	2.6 c	2.0	25.7 d	32.4 d	29.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CRU 4.5%	2.6 b	3.6 b	3.1	64.5 c	95.2 a	79.8	45.1	73.0	59.1	14.7	11.7	13.2	30.5	41.7	36.1
CRU 6%	3.3 a	4.0 b	3.7	75.0 a	88.4 b	81.7	57.3	65.1	61.2	22.3	16.6	19.5	38.1	46.6	42.4
SPAD-35 N	2.6 b	4.5 a	3.6	70.0 b	88.8 b	79.4	88.6	86.8	87.7	25.0	30.2	27.6	52.2	69.8	61.0
PU-2 splits	2.6 b	3.8 b	3.2	60.7 c	74.0 c	67.4	35.0	41.6	38.3	12.6	12.5	12.6	26.2	38.3	32.3
Mean	2.5	3.7	3.1	59.2	75.7	67.5	56.5	66.6	61.6	18.6	17.8	18.2	36.8	49.1	43.0
CD ^e (5%)															
Varieties	0.2	0.2		1.8	2.4										
Treatments	0.3	0.3		2.3	3.1										
Varieties × treatments	0.6	0.5		4.0	5.4										

^aTreatment means within each variety followed by the same letter are not significantly different at CD 5% probability level. ^bRecovery efficiency: ($\Sigma r = \Delta$ plant N uptake/N applied). ^cAEN = additional grain yield over control per kilogram N applied. ^dPFP-N = total grain yield per kilogram N applied. ^eCD = critical difference.

The interaction between rice cultivars and N treatments was significant for grain yield in both seasons. The highest grain yield of 6.8 t ha⁻¹ was recorded in Ajaya given CRU 6% and SPAD-35 N treatments during the winter season. The N recovery (mean of two seasons) was highest in SPAD-35 N, followed by CRU 6% in all three cultivars; this was probably due to the congruence of N supply with crop demand.

The highest SPAD values were observed at the maximum tillering stage for all varieties (Table 2). SPAD values recorded at critical crop growth stages were higher for CRU 6% and SPAD-35 N treatments than for PU-2 splits. The higher SPAD values indicate a higher foliar N concentration that led to higher grain yield, plant N uptake, fertilizer N recovery, and efficiency with CRU 6% and SPAD-35 N treatments. The highest total N uptake by all varieties recorded in the CRU 6% treatment indicated that this controlled-release fertilizer maintained a steady N

Table 2. SPAD values at critical growth stages of three rice varieties as influenced by various N treatments, DRR farm, Andhra Pradesh, India, 1997-98 cropping seasons.

Treatment	Maximum tillering			Panicle initiation			Heading		
	1997 kharif	1997-98 rabi	Mean	1997 kharif	1997-98 rabi	Mean	1997 kharif	1997-98 rabi	Mean
Rasi									
Control	30.6	32.1	31.3	31.6	32.0	31.8	29.7	28.3	29.0
CRU 4.5%	44.6	38.4	41.5	36.8	37.5	37.2	34.1	33.2	33.7
CRU 6%	39.7	38.2	39.0	39.9	40.3	40.1	36.2	35.7	36.0
SPAD-35 N	38.7	40.2	39.5	38.1	39.0	38.6	34.7	34.0	34.4
PU-2 splits	39.3	38.9	39.1	37.4	37.0	37.2	29.7	28.8	29.3
PU-basal	39.5	35.9	37.7	35.6	33.1	34.4	29.7	28.8	29.3
Ajaya									
Control	31.0	32.3	31.6	30.5	29.0	29.8	30.8	30.1	30.5
CRU 4.5%	40.3	38.2	39.3	32.2	31.8	32.0	32.4	32.5	32.5
CRU 6%	41.1	41.1	41.1	35.5	35.0	35.3	35.6	33.2	34.4
SPAD-35 N	38.0	38.7	38.4	35.5	40.6	38.1	34.0	34.7	34.4
PU-2 splits	38.8	39.8	39.3	33.6	32.3	33.0	32.7	30.9	31.8
PU-basal	39.8	38.6	39.2	32.9	33.5	33.2	30.1	30.0	30.5
Pusa Basmati									
Control	33.0	32.0	32.5	33.0	31.3	32.2	34.0	33.2	33.6
CRU 4.5%	42.8	39.5	41.2	37.4	36.2	36.8	37.9	35.3	36.6
CRU 6%	42.8	42.1	42.4	38.8	38.0	38.4	36.1	37.4	36.8
SPAD-35 N	43.1	37.4	40.3	36.0	41.3	38.7	37.1	38.7	37.9
PU-2 splits	40.4	34.9	37.7	36.8	35.9	36.3	38.2	33.2	35.7
PU-basal	41.1	41.1	41.1	35.7	33.8	34.8	36.0	30.4	33.2

supply to the crop throughout the growth period.

These observations confirm that the use of CRU 6% fertilizer and the chlorophyll meter technique (SPAD-N) produces high grain yields with high N uptake and efficiency. CRU 6% also appeared to be better than CRU 4.5%, probably due to its slower N release profile. If CRU could be priced competitively with the commonly available PU, it could become the preferred N fertilizer for rice.

Real-time N management using the chlorophyll meter and PU represents an attractive alternative for improving grain yields and N use efficiency in rice.

References

Balasubramanian V, Morales AC, Cruz RT, Abdulrachman S. 1999. On-farm adaptation of knowledge-intensive nitrogen management technologies for rice systems. *Nutr. Cycl. Agroecosyst.* 53:59-69.

De Datta SK, Buresh RJ. 1989. Integrated nitrogen management in irrigated rice. *Adv. Soil Sci.* 10:143-169.

Katyal JC, Singh B, Sharma VK, Grasswell ET. 1985. Efficiency of some modified urea fertilizer for lowland rice grown on a permeable soil. *Fert. Res.* 6:279-290.

Kumar V, Shrotriya GC, Kaore SV, editors. 1989. Soil fertility and fertilizer use. Vol. III. Urea supergranules for increasing nitrogen use efficiency. New Delhi (India): Indian Farmers Fertilizer Cooperative. 143 p.

Peng S, Garcia FV, Laza RC, Sanico AL, Visperas RM, Cassman KG. 1996. Increased N-use efficiency using a chlorophyll meter on high-yielding irrigated rice. *Field Crops Res.* 47:243-252.

Assessment of chlorophyll meter-based N application at critical growth stages of irrigated transplanted rice

S.P. Ramanathan and R. Nagarajan, SWMRI, Thanjavur, India; and V. Balasubramanian, IRRI

Synchronizing nitrogen (N) application with crop demand and soil N supply is one strategy for improving N use efficiency (NUE) in rice. Using a variable N rate application based on observed chlorophyll meter readings at critical growth stages may help optimize grain yield and NUE at the same time. The chlorophyll or SPAD meter can accurately measure leaf chlorophyll content that is related to leaf N status. It could help develop need-based N fertilization in rice (Peng et al 1996). One disadvantage of the SPAD technique, however, is the need for weekly observations to monitor crop N status, which could sometimes lead to many (3–6) split N applications (Balasubramanian et al 1999).

Field experiments were conducted during the 1997-98 dry (DS, kuruvai: June to September) and wet (WS-II, thaladi: October to February) seasons at the SWMRI farm in Thanjavur, India. The objective was to determine whether chlorophyll meter readings taken only at critical crop growth stages—early tillering, active tillering, panicle initiation, and 10% flowering—were sufficient, and to apply variable rates of N based on a range of SPAD threshold values (Table 1) rather than on a single critical SPAD value. The effect of variable rate N application, based on a range of chlorophyll meter readings, on

grain yield and NUE was measured in these trials. Treatments included different ranges of SPAD threshold values: <32, 33–35, and 36–38. Rice varieties ADT42 (115 d) and ADT38 (135 d) were used during the DS and WS-II, respectively. Treatments were arranged in a completely randomized block design with seven replications.

SPAD readings were taken in all treatments at critical crop growth stages using the youngest fully expanded leaf of 10 randomly selected plants from each plot. Whenever average SPAD readings fell within a set range of threshold values, N was applied immediately based on the variable rates specified in Table 1. Plant N status was allowed to fall to the specific range of SPAD values for each treatment before N was applied.

Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) was determined at 14% moisture content from three 5-m² sample areas taken from each plot. The NUE

is expressed as the partial factor productivity of applied N (PFP-N).

Grain yields were low in both the 1997-98 DS and WS due to heavy flooding at critical crop growth stages. Among the SPAD threshold ranges used in the DS, the 36–38 range gave the highest grain yield (4.9 t ha⁻¹), but it was not significantly different from that of SPAD <32 (4.7 t ha⁻¹) or 33–35 (4.6 t ha⁻¹) (Table 2). The NUE as expressed by the PFP-N value was 125 for SPAD <32, 92 for SPAD 33–36, and 54 for SPAD 36–38. The data seem to indicate that a SPAD threshold range of 36–38 could be optimum for DS rice crops. Further research is ongoing to confirm these results.

In the WS, the highest grain yield was obtained from SPAD 36–38; this was not significantly different from that of SPAD 33–35, but significantly different from that of SPAD <32 (Table 2). More N

Table 1. Amount of N applied (kg ha⁻¹) based on range of SPAD threshold values observed at critical crop growth stages.

Range of SPAD threshold values	Early tillering (14 DAT)*	Active tillering (28 DAT)	Panicle initiation (42 DAT)	Flowering (56 DAT)
<32	30	50	50	30
33–35	30	40	40	30
36–38	20	30	30	20

*DAT = d after transplanting.